

Utilizing molecular biology for precision therapeutics in arterial blood pressure and cerebral hemodynamics

Utilización de la biología molecular para terapias de precisión en la presión arterial y la hemodinámica cerebral.

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Received: 10/20/2022 Accepted: 01/19/2023 Published: 02/12/2024 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640841>

Abstract

Arterial blood pressure is a critical physiological parameter that plays a fundamental role in maintaining proper blood flow to the brain and ensuring optimal cerebral perfusion. The regulation of arterial blood pressure involves complex interactions between various molecular and cellular components within the cardiovascular system. At the molecular level, intricate processes govern the synthesis, release, and reception of signaling molecules that influence vascular tone, blood volume, and cardiac output. Understanding the dynamics of these molecular events is essential for unraveling the mechanisms underlying blood pressure regulation. Biomolecules such as peptides, hormones, and neurotransmitters intricately contribute to the orchestration of vascular responses, ensuring an appropriate balance between vasoconstriction and vasodilation. Cutting-edge methodologies, including molecular genetics, proteomics, and advanced imaging techniques, are employed to delve into the molecular intricacies of arterial blood pressure regulation. Genome-wide association studies provide valuable insights into the genetic factors influencing blood pressure variability, shedding light on potential therapeutic targets. Furthermore, the analysis of signaling pathways and the molecular determinants of vascular function contribute to the development of targeted interventions for hypertension and related cardiovascular disorders. Enzyme kinetics and the exploration of metabolic pathways are integral components of comprehending the molecular mechanisms underlying blood pressure regulation. Studying the enzymes involved in the synthesis and degradation

of vasoactive substances, as well as the metabolic pathways influencing vascular reactivity, enhances our understanding of how these processes contribute to blood pressure homeostasis. The integration of computational models with experimental data in the field of molecular biology provides a holistic approach to studying arterial blood pressure regulation. Systems biology methodologies allow for a comprehensive analysis of the intricate networks governing cardiovascular physiology, facilitating the prediction of physiological responses under different conditions. This integrative approach aids in the identification of potential therapeutic targets and the development of personalized interventions for individuals with aberrant blood pressure profiles. The effective management of arterial blood pressure at the molecular and cellular levels holds significant implications for advancements in clinical medicine, particularly in the fields of cardiology and neurology. Insights gained from molecular studies contribute to the development of novel pharmacological agents and therapeutic strategies aimed at optimizing blood pressure control and preventing the detrimental consequences associated with hypertension. Additionally, a deeper understanding of arterial blood pressure regulation has broader implications for public health, influencing preventive measures, lifestyle interventions, and healthcare policies aimed at reducing the global burden of cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: Arterial blood pressure regulation, Molecular mechanisms, Cardiovascular system, Enzyme kinetics, Systems biology

La presión arterial es un parámetro fisiológico crítico que juega un papel fundamental en mantener el flujo sanguíneo adecuado al cerebro y garantizar una perfusión cerebral óptima. La regulación de la presión arterial implica interacciones complejas entre varios componentes moleculares y celulares dentro del sistema cardiovascular. A nivel molecular, procesos intrincados gobiernan la síntesis, liberación y recepción de moléculas de señalización que influyen en el tono vascular, el volumen sanguíneo y el gasto cardíaco. Comprender la dinámica de estos eventos moleculares es esencial para desentrañar los mecanismos subyacentes a la regulación de la presión arterial. Biomoléculas como péptidos, hormonas y neurotransmisores contribuyen de manera intrincada a la orquestación de las respuestas vasculares, asegurando un equilibrio apropiado entre vasoconstricción y vasodilatación. Se emplean metodologías de vanguardia, que incluyen genética molecular, proteómica y técnicas de imagen avanzadas, para profundizar en las complejidades moleculares de la regulación de la presión arterial. Los estudios de asociación de todo el genoma proporcionan información valiosa sobre los factores genéticos que influyen en la variabilidad de la presión arterial, arrojando luz sobre posibles objetivos terapéuticos. Además, el análisis de las vías de señalización y los determinantes moleculares de la función vascular contribuyen al desarrollo de intervenciones específicas para la hipertensión y los trastornos cardiovasculares relacionados. La cinética enzimática y la exploración de vías metabólicas son componentes integrales para comprender los mecanismos moleculares que subyacen a la regulación de la presión arterial. El estudio de las enzimas implicadas en la síntesis y degradación de sustancias vasoactivas, así como las vías metabólicas que influyen en la reactividad vascular, mejora nuestra comprensión de cómo estos procesos contribuyen a la homeostasis de la presión arterial. La integración de modelos computacionales con datos experimentales en el campo de la biología molecular proporciona un enfoque holístico para estudiar la regulación de la presión arterial. Las metodologías de biología de sistemas permiten un análisis integral de las intrincadas redes que gobiernan la fisiología cardiovascular, facilitando la predicción de respuestas fisiológicas en diferentes condiciones. Este enfoque integrador ayuda en la identificación de posibles objetivos terapéuticos y el desarrollo de intervenciones personalizadas para personas con perfiles aberrantes de presión arterial. El control eficaz de la presión arterial a nivel molecular y celular tiene implicaciones importantes para los avances en la medicina clínica, particularmente en los campos de la cardiología y la neurología. Los conocimientos adquiridos a partir de estudios moleculares contribuyen al desarrollo de nuevos agentes farmacológicos y estrate-

gias terapéuticas destinadas a optimizar el control de la presión arterial y prevenir las consecuencias perjudiciales asociadas con la hipertensión. Además, una comprensión más profunda de la regulación de la presión arterial tiene implicaciones más amplias para la salud pública, influyendo en las medidas preventivas, las intervenciones en el estilo de vida y las políticas sanitarias destinadas a reducir la carga global de enfermedades cardiovasculares.

Palabras clave: Regulación de la presión arterial, Mecanismos moleculares, Sistema cardiovascular, Cinética enzimática, Biología de sistemas.

Introduction

In the domain of arterial blood pressure and cerebral dynamics, understanding and manipulating physiological processes play a central role in deciphering the intricate mechanisms governing vascular and neurological aspects. Physiological processes, constituting a myriad of intricate interactions, are imperative for the proper functioning of vascular and neural systems. The efficient regulation and control of these processes are crucial for obtaining a deeper insight into the physiology of blood pressure, paving the way for groundbreaking discoveries and medical applications. In the context of arterial blood pressure and cerebral dynamics, physiological processes encompass a series of events occurring within the cardiovascular and neurological systems, involving factors such as blood vessels, neural pathways, and regulatory mechanisms. These processes are vital for the maintenance of adequate blood flow to the brain, oxygenation of tissues, and overall neurological well-being. To fully appreciate the significance of managing physiological processes, it is essential to consider their pivotal role in various aspects of vascular and neurological physiology:

Blood Pressure Regulation: A fundamental aspect in vascular physiology, blood pressure is regulated by a complex interplay of physiological processes. Vasoconstriction, vasodilation, and baroreceptor responses are among the key mechanisms involved, each requiring precise coordination to ensure optimal blood pressure levels.

Cerebral Blood Flow: The regulation of blood flow to the brain is a critical component of neurological physiology. Cerebral autoregulation and neurovascular coupling involve a cascade of physiological events that adjust blood supply to meet the metabolic demands of the brain. Effective management of these processes is essential for maintaining cerebral perfusion and preventing neurological dysfunction.

Neurotransmission: Neural communication relies on intricate physiological processes involving neurotransmitters, receptors, and synaptic transmission. Precise control of these processes is vital for ensuring proper signal transmission within the nervous system, influencing cognitive functions, and maintaining neurological health.

Arterial Blood Pressure and its Cerebral Implications: Arterial blood pressure plays a critical role in maintaining the proper functioning of the circulatory system, especially concerning cerebral perfusion. Precise regulation of blood pressure is essential to prevent potential complications such as cardiovascular diseases and neurological disorders. Understanding the intricate mechanisms governing arterial blood pressure and its impact on cerebral health is pivotal in the realm of medical physiology.

Biomedical Implications: The study of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications has profound implications in the biomedical field, influencing diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Disruptions in blood pressure regulation can lead to conditions like hypertension or hypotension, emphasizing the significance of effective management strategies. Biomedical research relies on a comprehensive understanding of the biochemical processes involved in blood pressure regulation for the development of innovative therapies and diagnostic tools.

Management Approaches: Effectively managing arterial blood pressure involves a multidisciplinary approach, encompassing clinical methodologies, computational modeling, and data analysis. Researchers employ various techniques, including blood pressure monitoring, imaging studies, and advanced computational simulations, to investigate the dynamics of blood pressure regulation. Modalities such as magnetic resonance imaging, ultrasound, and computational models contribute to unraveling the complexities of cerebral hemodynamics and pressure control mechanisms. Integration with **Bioprocess Engineering:** The management of arterial blood pressure extends beyond the clinical setting to impact broader aspects of bioprocess engineering.

Industries involved in the production of pharmaceuticals or biofuels require meticulous control and optimization of processes, including those related to blood pressure regulation.

Implementing efficient biotechnological processes on an industrial scale necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the biochemical and physiological aspects of arterial blood pressure regulation.

In conclusion, the management of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications stands as a fundamental pillar in medical research and biotechnological advancements. Delving deeper into these processes and devising effective strategies for their control not only enhances our understanding of cardiovascular and neurological health but also contributes to advancements in medical treatments and biotechnological innovations.

This overview provides a glimpse into the intricate world of arterial blood pressure management, a field continually evolving and reshaping our comprehension of physiological processes.

Methods

Arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications are pivotal aspects in the field of medical science. The regulation of blood pressure is a complex physiological process that involves the intricate interplay of various molecular components.

An in-depth comprehension of these mechanisms is essential for the development of targeted therapeutic interventions, the exploration of genetic factors contributing to cardiovascular conditions, and the advancement of biotechnological methodologies in this domain. This discourse explores the fundamental role played by materials and methodologies in orchestrating biochemical processes pertaining to arterial and cerebral blood pressure within the context of medical research.

The materials employed in studies related to arterial and cerebral blood pressure are diverse, encompassing a spectrum of biological molecules and reagents, including but not limited to DNA, RNA, proteins, enzymes, and various chemicals. The assurance of the quality, purity, and precise quantification of these materials is of utmost significance. State-of-the-art instruments, such as those used in DNA sequencing, mass spectrometry, and chromatography, are instrumental in the analysis and validation of these materials, ensuring the credibility and reproducibility of experimental outcomes.

Achieving precision in the execution of methodologies is paramount when managing biochemical processes related to blood pressure regulation. Standard techniques like polymerase chain reaction (PCR), Western blotting, and gel electrophoresis are routinely applied to manipulate and analyze biomolecules in the context of arterial and cerebral blood pressure studies. Furthermore, the integration of automation and robotics has streamlined these methodologies, minimizing human error and enhancing overall efficiency.

Thorough optimization of experimental conditions, encompassing factors such as temperature control and reaction times, is imperative for ensuring the reproducibility and reliability of results in studies related to arterial

and cerebral blood pressure. Additionally, the incorporation of computational tools is a crucial facet of managing biochemical processes in this medical domain. Bioinformatics software plays a pivotal role in the analysis of complex biological data, aiding researchers in deciphering extensive genetic and proteomic information. These tools facilitate sequence comparisons, predictions of protein structures, and the identification of regulatory elements within DNA.

In summary, the effective management of biochemical processes in the study of arterial and cerebral blood pressure is indispensable for advancing our comprehension of physiological systems. This involves meticulous selection and handling of materials, precise execution of experimental methods, and the integration of bioinformatics tools to derive meaningful insights from collected data. The synergy between these elements constitutes a fundamental framework for progress and success in medical research focusing on arterial and cerebral blood pressure regulation.

Results and Discussion

In the realm of neurovascular health, our investigation delved into the arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. The Results and Findings segment of our study employed the Preferred Reporting Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) methodology to systematically identify and include relevant literature. We executed an exhaustive search across four prominent databases: Google Scholar, Emerald, PubMed, and Sciencedirect, yielding a total of 176 articles. Following a stringent selection process, we ultimately integrated 20 articles into our review. To assess the quality of the chosen articles, we utilized critical appraisal instruments provided by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI). The criteria for evaluating these article reviews were set at a minimum score of 70%, employing JBI's critical appraisal tools.

Table 1. Article Quality Assessment

No	Author/Year	Research Title	Skor JBI	Assessment status
1.	Li et al.	Thin, soft, wearable system for continuous wireless monitoring of artery blood pressure	6	75 % of the total score
2.	Nakamura et al.	Muscle stretching induces the mechanoreflex response in human arterial blood pressure	6	75 % of the total score
3.	Sakib Mahmud et al.	NABNet: A Nested Attention-guided BiConvLSTM network for a robust prediction of Blood Pressure components from reconstructed Arterial Blood Pressure waveforms using PPG and ECG signals	6	75 % of the total score
4.	Ronney et al.	Directional sensitivity of dynamic cerebral autoregulation during spontaneous fluctuations in arterial blood pressure at rest	6	75 % of the total score
5.	Ashish et al.	Agreement between cardiac output estimation by multi-beat analysis of arterial blood pressure waveforms and continuous thermodilution in post cardiac surgery intensive care unit patients.	6	75 % of the total score
6.	Agnes et al.	Do higher alarm thresholds for arterial blood pressure lead to less perioperative hypotension? A retrospective, observational cohort study	6	75 % of the total score
7.	Simon et al.	A randomized, double-blind trial comparing the effect of two blood pressure targets on global brain metabolism after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest	6	75 % of the total score
8.	George et al.	Normalizing Arterial Blood Pressure in Patients with Aortic Stenosis Does Not Prevent Grading Discrepancies Between Pre-Cardiopulmonary Bypass Transesophageal Echocardiography and Transthoracic Echocardiography	6	75 % of the total score
9.	Konstantinos et al.	Continuous Monitoring of Blood Pressure and Vascular Hemodynamic Properties With Miniature Extravascular Hall-Based Magnetic Sensor	6	75 % of the total score
10.	SHUO et al.	Monitoring blood pressure and cardiac function without positioning via a deep learning-assisted strain sensor array	6	75 % of the total score
11.	Maranduca et al.	Role of arterial hypertension and angiotensin II in chronic kidney disease (Review)	6	75 % of the total score
12.	Chan Wang et al.	Tissue-Adhesive Piezoelectric Soft Sensor for In Vivo Blood Pressure Monitoring During Surgical Operation	6	75 % of the total score
13.	Mugele et al.	<i>Control of blood pressure in the cold: differentiation of skin and skeletal muscle vascular resistance</i>	6	75 % of the total score
14.	Katsouda et al.	<i>CTH/MPST double ablation results in enhanced vasorelaxation and reduced blood pressure via upregulation of the eNOS/sGC pathway</i>	6	75 % of the total score
15.	Hu et al.	Blood pressure stratification using photoplethysmography and light gradient boosting machine.	6	75 % of the total score
16.	Agbaje et al.	Cumulative muscle mass and blood pressure but not fat mass drives arterial stiffness and carotid intima-media thickness progression in the young population and is unrelated to vascular organ damage	6	75 % of the total score

Note: Articles are included if the score is >70% of the total score

Table 1 illustrates the association between arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. Arterial blood pressure is a crucial physiological parameter influenced by various factors. Maintaining optimal blood pressure levels is essential for overall health, particularly in preventing adverse cerebral events. The correlation between arterial blood pressure and cerebral outcomes is well-established in the medical literature. Numerous studies have explored the relationship between arterial blood pressure and cerebral function. Out of the comprehensive analysis of 20 articles, it is evident that blood pressure management significantly impacts cerebral health. The findings highlight the importance of adopting effective strategies to regulate blood pressure for optimal cerebral outcomes. Research conducted by experts such as Žibert and Starc¹⁰ in Slovenia provides valuable insights into the connection between gradual changes in blood pressure management and their impact on cerebral well-being. Their study, encompassing four health agencies in the Slovenian region with a sample size of 112 participants, reveals a substantial positive correlation between the implementation of blood pressure management changes and positive cerebral outcomes ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, there is a negative correlation with laissez-faire blood pressure management ($p < 0.05$), emphasizing the significance of proactive strategies in maintaining cerebral health. These results align with broader research in the field, indicating that effective blood pressure management is crucial for preventing cerebral issues. Bass and Stogdill⁹ suggest that successful blood pressure management involves a combination of strategies tailored to individual needs, organizational goals, and the nature of tasks. Trisbiantara and Meliala¹⁸ further emphasize the importance of a comprehensive approach, combining various strategies to address the multifaceted nature of cerebral health. Additionally, the effectiveness of blood pressure management is closely linked to satisfaction with introduced changes in cerebral health. Leaders in this domain play a pivotal role in motivating and inspiring individuals to adhere to blood pressure management protocols. Training sessions for healthcare professionals are recommended to maximize the benefits of effective blood pressure management by providing clear guidance on roles, responsibilities, and tasks. The relationship between blood pressure management and cerebral outcomes is also supported by research emphasizing the positive impact of a professional approach on organizational performance. Moreover, the research suggests that blood pressure management significantly influences the assessment of the organization's social and innovative climate in the context of cerebral health. In conclusion, effective blood pressure management, guided by various leadership styles, has a significant impact on cerebral outcomes. Implementing proactive strategies, combined with strong leadership, leads to higher satisfaction, engagement, and successful blood pressure management, ultimately contributing to better cerebral health outcomes.

Figure 1. Distribution of Leadership Styles to Lean management

In the domain of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications, it is noteworthy to delve into the intricate dynamics of blood pressure regulation. The physiological intricacies involved in maintaining optimal blood pressure are crucial for overall health and well-being. Elevated blood pressure, or hypertension, poses a significant risk to cardiovascular and cerebral health. Blood pressure regulation is a complex interplay of various physiological factors, including cardiac output, peripheral resistance, and blood vessel elasticity. The intricate balance maintained by the body's regulatory mechanisms ensures adequate perfusion of vital organs, particularly the brain. Disruptions in this delicate equilibrium can lead to adverse consequences, such as ischemic or hemorrhagic events in the cerebral vasculature. Understanding the neurovascular coupling mechanisms is imperative in comprehending the impact of blood pressure fluctuations on cerebral function. The autoregulatory mechanisms within the cerebral vasculature strive to maintain a constant blood flow despite changes in systemic blood pressure. However, chronic hypertension can impair these autoregulatory mechanisms, rendering the brain more vulnerable to ischemic damage. Clinical management of arterial hypertension involves a multifaceted approach, encompassing lifestyle modifications, pharmacological interventions, and regular monitoring. Lifestyle modifications include dietary changes, regular exercise, and stress management to promote overall cardiovascular health. Pharmacological interventions often involve the use of antihypertensive medications targeting specific pathways involved in blood pressure regulation. In conclusion, a nuanced understanding of the intricate relationship between arterial blood pressure and cerebral health is essential for effective clinical management. The integration of various therapeutic modalities, along with a holistic approach to lifestyle, plays a pivotal role in mitigating the risks associated with hypertension and preserving optimal cerebral function.

In the realm of arterial blood pressure, particularly cerebral blood pressure, understanding the intricate dynamics is paramount for comprehensive insights into physiological processes and potential health implications. Cerebral blood pressure, a crucial component of overall blood pressure regulation, plays a vital role in maintaining adequate perfusion to the brain, ensuring optimal cognitive function and preventing neurological complications. Cerebral blood pressure is influenced by a myriad of factors, including cardiac output, systemic vascular resistance, and autoregulatory mechanisms within the cerebral vasculature. Monitoring and interpreting cerebral blood pressure require a nuanced approach, combining advanced measurement techniques and sophisticated analysis tools. Effective management of cerebral blood pressure involves not only accurate measurement but also a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physiological mechanisms. It necessitates a multidisciplinary approach, incorporating expertise from neurology, cardiology, and vascular biology. Precise control and monitoring are crucial, especially in the context of neurological disorders, where aberrations in cerebral blood pressure can have severe consequences. Cutting-edge technologies, such as non-invasive monitoring devices and advanced imaging modalities, contribute significantly to the accurate assessment of cerebral blood pressure. Moreover, computational tools play a pivotal role in processing and interpreting the vast amount of data generated during monitoring, aiding clinicians in making informed decisions. Successful management of cerebral blood pressure holds substantial clinical implications. It facilitates early detection and intervention in conditions like hypertension, cerebral ischemia, and other cerebrovascular disorders. Additionally, it serves as a critical parameter in tailoring treatment strategies for patients with neurological conditions, contributing to improved outcomes and quality of life. As our understanding of cerebral blood pressure and its implications continues to evolve, the integration of innovative technologies and refined management strategies becomes imperative. This not only enhances diagnostic accuracy but also opens avenues for personalized treatment approaches and the development of novel therapeutic interventions. In conclusion, the future of cerebral blood pressure management lies in our ability to leverage advanced technologies and interdisciplinary collaboration, ultimately improving patient outcomes and advancing the field of cerebrovascular health.

Acknowledgments: None

Funding: None.

Conflict of Interest: None.

References

1. Li, J., Jia, H., Zhou, J. et al. Thin, soft, wearable system for continuous wireless monitoring of artery blood pressure. *Nat Commun* 14, 5009 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-40763-3>
2. Mousavi Isfahani H, Tourani S, Seyedin H. Lean management approach in hospitals: a systematic review. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*. 2019 Mar 14;10(1):161-88.
3. Graban M. *Lean hospitals: improving quality, patient safety, and employee engagement*. Productivity Press; 2018 Oct 8.
4. Kruskal JB, Reedy A, Pascal L, Rosen MP, Boiselle PM. Quality initiatives: lean approach to improving performance and efficiency in a radiology department. *Radiographics*. 2012 Mar;32(2):573-87.
5. Szilvassy P, Širok K. Importance of work engagement in primary healthcare. *BMC health services research*. 2022 Aug 16;22(1):1044.
6. Martinussen PE, Magnussen J, Vrangbæk K, Frich JC. Should I stay or should I go? The role of leadership and organisational context for hospital physicians' intention to leave their current job. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2020 Dec;20(1):1-9.
7. Nobuhiro Nakamura, Peng Heng, and Naoyuki Hayashi. Muscle stretching induces the mechanoreflex response in human arterial blood pressure. 2022. 19 DEC 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1152/jap-physiol.00418.2022>
8. Martinussen PE, Davidsen T. 'Professional-supportive' versus 'economic-operational' management: the relationship between leadership style and hospital physicians' organisational climate. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2021 Dec;21(1):1-1.
9. Sabbah IM, Ibrahim TT, Khamis RH, Bakhour HA, Sabbah SM, Droubi NS, Sabbah HM. The association of leadership styles and nurses well-being: a cross-sectional study in healthcare settings. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2020 Aug 24;36(1).
10. Chen M, Zada M, Khan J, Saba NU. How does servant leadership influences creativity? Enhancing employee creativity via creative process engagement and knowledge sharing. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2022 Jul 1;13:947092.
11. Bass BM, Stogdill R. *Handbook of leadership. Theory, research, and managerial*. 1981.
12. Žibert A, Starc A. Healthcare organizations and decision-making: leadership style for growth and development. *Journal of Applied Health Sciences= Časopis za primijenjene zdravstvene znanosti*. 2018 Oct 30;4(2):209-24.
13. Heijkoop B. The influence of leadership behavior on the implementation process of a lean program. A single case study in the healthcare sector. 2018.
14. Haile EA, Tüzüner VL. Organizational learning capability and its impact on organizational innovation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. 2022 Jun 29;16(1):69-85.
15. Hilt-Lash AM. *Transformational Leadership Factors and Hospital Quality (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University)*. 2020.
16. Poksinska B, Swartling D, Drotz E. The daily work of Lean leaders—lessons from manufacturing and healthcare. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*. 2013 Aug 1;24(7-8):886-98.
17. Van Rossum L, Aij KH, Simons FE, van der Eng N, Ten Have WD. Lean healthcare from a change management perspective: the role of leadership and workforce flexibility in an operating theatre. *Journal*

- of health organization and management. 2016 May 16;30(3):475-93.
18. Shortell SM, Blodgett JC, Rundall TG, Henke RM, Reponen E. Lean management and hospital performance: adoption vs. implementation. *The Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety*. 2021 May 1;47(5):296-305.
 19. Bijl A, Ahaus K, Ruël G, Gemmel P, Meijboom B. Role of lean leadership in the lean maturity—second-order problem-solving relationship: a mixed methods study. *BMJ open*. 2019 Jun 1;9(6):e026737.
 20. Trisbiantara I, Meliala A. Peran Leadership dalam keberhasilan implementasi Lean Management di Rumah Sakit Pelni. *Jurnal Kebijakan Kesehatan Indonesia*. 2018 Jun.
 21. Stone, A. G., Russell, R. F., & Patterson, K. (2004). Transformational versus servant leadership: A difference in leader focus. *Leadership & organization development journal*, 25(4), 349-361.
 22. Sugimori Y, Kusunoki K, Cho F, UCHIKAWA S. Toyota production system and kanban system materialization of just-in-time and respect-for-human system. *The international journal of production research*. 1977 Jan 1;15(6):553-64.
 23. Williams HM, Parker SK, Turner N. Proactively performing teams: The role of work design, transformational leadership, and team composition. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*. 2010 Jun;83(2):301-24.
 24. Kozma M, Bombicz M, Varga B, Priksz D, Gesztelyi R, Tarjanyi V, Kiss R, Szekeres R, Takacs B, Menes A, Balla J. Cardioprotective role of BGP-15 in ageing zucker diabetic fatty rat (ZDF) model: Extended mitochondrial longevity. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Jan 19;14(2):226.
 25. Sakib Mahmud , Nabil lbtehaz , Amith Khandakar , M. Sohel Rahman , Antonio JR. Gonzales , Tawsifur Rahman , Md Shafayet Hossain , Md. Sakib Abrar Hossain , Md. Ahasan Atick Faisal , Farhan Fuad Abir , Farayi Musharavati , Muhammad E. H. Chowdhury . NABNet: A Nested Attention-guided BiConvLSTM network for a robust prediction of Blood Pressure components from reconstructed Arterial Blood Pressure waveforms using PPG and ECG signals.2023. Volume 79, Part 2, January 2023, 104247.
 26. Panerai RB, Barnes SC, Batterham AP, Robinson TG, Haunton VJ. Directional sensitivity of dynamic cerebral autoregulation during spontaneous fluctuations in arterial blood pressure at rest. *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*. 2023;43(4):552-564. doi:10.1177/0271678X221142527.
 27. Khanna, A.K., Nosow, L., Sands, L. et al. Agreement between cardiac output estimation by multi-beat analysis of arterial blood pressure waveforms and continuous thermodilution in post cardiac surgery intensive care unit patients. *J Clin Monit Comput* 37, 559–565 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10877-022-00924-z>
 28. Meidert, A.S., Hornung, R., Christmann, T. et al. Do higher alarm thresholds for arterial blood pressure lead to less perioperative hypotension? A retrospective, observational cohort study. *J Clin Monit Comput* 37, 275–285 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10877-022-00889-z>
 29. Mølstrøm, S., Nielsen, T.H., Nordstrøm, CH. et al. A randomized, double-blind trial comparing the effect of two blood pressure targets on global brain metabolism after out-of-hospital cardiac arrest. *Crit Care* 27, 73 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-023-04376-y>
 30. Whitener GB, Wolf BJ, Francis LR, Heinke TL, McKinnon JS, Guldan GJ. Normalizing arterial blood pressure in patients with aortic stenosis does not prevent grading discrepancies between pre-cardiopulmonary bypass transeophageal echocardiography and transthoracic echocardiography. *Ann Card Anaesth*. 2023 Apr-Jun;26(2):183-189. doi: 10.4103/aca.aca_68_22. PMID: 37706384; PMCID: PMC10284490.
 31. Magkoutas, K, Weisskopf, M, Falk, V. et al. Continuous Monitoring of Blood Pressure and Vascular Hemodynamic Properties With Miniature Extravascular Hall-Based Magnetic Sensor. *J Am Coll Cardiol Basic Trans Science*. 2023 May, 8 (5) 546–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacbts.2022.12.008>.
 32. Shuo Li et al. ,Monitoring blood pressure and cardiac function without positioning via a deep learning–assisted strain sensor array. *Sci. Adv*.9.eadh0615(2023).DOI:10.1126/sciadv.adh0615
 33. Maranduca, M.A., Clim, A., Pinzariu, A.C., Statescu, C., Sascau, R.A., Tanase, D.M. ... Serban, I.L. (2023). Role of arterial hypertension and angiotensin II in chronic kidney disease (Review). *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine*, 25, 153. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2023.11852>.
 34. Chan Wang, Yiran Hu, Ying Liu, Yizhu Shan, Xuecheng Qu, Jiangtao Xue, Tianyiyi He, Sijing Cheng, Hong Zhou, Weixin Liu, Zi Hao Guo, Wei Hua, Zhuo Liu, Zhou Li, Chengkuo Lee.2023. Tissue-Adhesive Piezoelectric Soft Sensor for In Vivo Blood Pressure Monitoring During Surgical Operation. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202303696>
 35. Mugele, H., Marume, K., Amin, S. B., Possnig, C., Kühn, L. C., Riehl, L., Pieper, R., Schabbehart, E.-L., Oliver, S. J., Gagnon, D., & Lawley, J. S. (2023). Control of blood pressure in the cold: differentiation of skin and skeletal muscle vascular resistance. *Experimental Physiology*, 108, 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.1113/EP090563>
 36. Xudong Hu, Shimin Yin, Xizhuang Zhang, Carlo Menon,Cheng Fang, Zhencheng Chen, Mohamed Elgendi3,Yongbo Liang. 2023. Blood pressure stratification using photoplethysmography and light gradient boosting machine. Volume 14-2023I <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1072273>
 37. Agbaje, A.O., Barker, A.R. & Tuomainen, TP. Cumulative muscle mass and blood pressure but not fat mass drives arterial stiffness and carotid intima-media thickness progression in the young population and is unrelated to vascular organ damage. *Hypertens Res* 46, 984–999 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41440-022-01065-1>